

NEWSLETTER

Allergy Cancer BioNano Research Centre

ACBN

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July – December 2021

Dear Alumni,

with our third Newsletter we present you some interesting *news* (and *olds*, if you like).

An “old friend” is about to retire, which is the **Christian Doppler Laboratory for Innovative Tools for Biosimilar Characterization**. In this edition Christian Huber gives an overview of the work that was performed in this highly successful project within the last eight years. Quite a few of you have been active in this CD lab and we cherish its great work, which has included training for 10 PhD students.

In fact, news is that ACBN is moving towards a stronger emphasis on data analysis, which is overall an important development in biological sciences. **Andreas Uhl from the Department of Computer Sciences** has joined ACBN in the beginning of this year. He is a leading expert in the processing of visual data and introduces you to his exciting research in his article.

ACBN contributes 1/7 of PLUS grant income

Albert Duschl

ACBN is in the process of undergoing its **regular evaluation**, which means that we had to summarize the accomplishments of ACBN in a **report from 2016-2020**. A weighty tome of 265 pages is now with the rectorate and will be shortly sent out to external evaluators. Here are some highlights: In these five years, the work groups within ACBN have published 423 papers, obtained 113 grants, filed 8 patents, awarded 63 PhDs and 104 Master degrees, employed 205 persons from grant money and obtained a grant income of € 15.8 Mio, which means that the 12 groups within ACBN have contributed **14.6% of the total grant income of the University** in this period.

An important development is that the **move of groups from Billrothstraße to the NaWi** (see our first Newsletter) has been completed this summer and they are now operating in completely new labs. We will show you some pictures in the next edition. Until then, enjoy a collection of photos from the NaWi and from the Itzling campus. Some motifs you will recognize, while others may be new to you.

Finally, we are still aiming at a physical meeting of Alumni at Salzburg, but since travel is still not fully possible, no date has been set so far. We will keep you updated.

Have a good, healthy and successful time, all the best,
Albert Duschl

In this edition you will find:

- ❖ The Christian Doppler Laboratory for Innovative Tools for Biosimilar Characterization: closing after eight successful years of operation in the challenging field of therapeutic protein characterization
- ❖ Analysis of Biomedical Visual Data: Model-based vs. Data Driven Research
- ❖ ACBN @ many (beautiful) places
- ❖ 400 years Paris Lodron University Salzburg

The Christian Doppler Laboratory for Innovative Tools for Biosimilar Characterization: closing after eight successful years of operation in the challenging field of therapeutic protein characterization

The story began in 2012, when Fátima (Ferreira), then vice rector of research at PLUS, animated me to initiate a Christian Doppler Laboratory at the University of Salzburg: “Christian, you have so many excellent connections to the pharmaceutical and instrument manufacturing industry. So, why don’t you try to set up a Christian Doppler Laboratory to intensify these collaborations?” I liked the idea a lot, and it did not take too much effort to find colleagues and industry partners interested in the topic of in-depth protein characterization. Colleagues at the Department of Molecular Biology (now Biosciences) joined readily and contributed their expertise: Hans Brandstetter in protein structural and functional analysis, Chiara Cabrele (later together with Mario Schubert) in polypeptide synthesis and modification as well as in nuclear magnetic resonance spectroscopy, Gabriele Gadermaier in protein expression and biochemical and functional protein characterization, Hanno Stutz in protein separations by electromigrative techniques, and finally, myself in protein separation and analysis by chromatography and mass spectrometry.

*Andreas Premstaller from Novartis,
Cornelia Weidemann from Thermo Fisher Scientific,
Governor of Salzburg Wilfried Haslauer
and Rector Heinrich Schmidinger (from left to right).*

CD Lab
opening in
2013

A former PhD student of mine in Innsbruck, and a former colleague in Saarbrücken, both in the meantime holding key positions at Sandoz Biopharmaceuticals (now Novartis) and Thermo Fisher Scientific, did not hesitate to support the idea on behalf of our favorite industry partners. The grant application was favorably evaluated and eventually, the Christian Doppler Laboratory for Innovative Tools for Biosimilar Characterization was officially opened in October 2013.

CD Lab researchers during a plenary meeting in July 2017.

The collaboration in the Christian Doppler Laboratory was extremely friendly and productive, leading to a number of novel tools for the characterization both of the structure and function of therapeutic proteins: the group of Hans Brandstetter invented a workflow of employing protein-modifying enzymes, termed “Analytical Cascade of Enzymes”, which is capable of literally highlighting minute structural and conformational differences between protein isoforms (the US patent was awarded in 2019).

The team around Gabriele Gadermaier was successful in selecting DNA-based aptamers selectively binding to substructures of antibody molecules from a ssDNA library containing about 10¹⁸ random 40-mer oligonucleotides. The aptamers were then shown to be applicable to the probing and distinction of different surface structures of stressed and unstressed protein therapeutics. Chiara Cabrele and Mario Schubert exploited their expertise in polypeptide synthesis and NMR spectroscopy under denaturing conditions to reveal and quantify posttranslational modifications such as oxidation, succinimide formation, glycosylation, internal hydrolysis or deamidation in a single NMR spectrum acquired under denaturing conditions. Capillary electrophoresis and capillary isoelectric focusing were finally developed in the group of Hanno Stutz into very sensitive sensors for protein charge and conformation. Finally, Mario Schubert and Gabriele Gadermaier developed a new method to map epitopes on antigens tightly interacting with intact monoclonal antibodies, which is called hydrogen/deuterium exchange memory (HDXMEM).

Julia Fegg's and Hans Brandstetter's view of how a cascade of enzymes can literally highlight small structural differences in proteins.

Therese Wohlschläger's and Ines Forstenlehner's mass spectrometric representation of more than 100 protein isoforms of the anti-inflammatory biotherapeutic Etanercept™.

After eight years, the most important lesson I have personally learnt as a naïve analytical chemist that I have to adjust my one-gene-one (or a few)-protein(s) view of protein expression into a one-gene-thousands of protein isoforms view. Thus, the most enlightening insight for me was not only that nature provides the tools to produce functional proteins in an enormous space of structural variability, but also that we can find ways to experimentally verify and characterize (at least part of) the complexity of proteoforms. This experimental proof of proteoform heterogeneity was well appreciated by the scientific community and led to the invitation to join an international panel of experts in protein characterization to collect a perspective article dealing with the question “How many protein isoforms are there”, which was published in *Nature Chemical Biology* and has been cited more than 320 times since publication in 2018. Learning from Hans' deep understanding of protein structure-function relationships it was a bit worrisome to me to realize that biopharmaceutical drugs are very often a mixture of an enormous number of different compounds of slightly different structure - and thus - function.

Another lesson learnt was the importance of meticulous interpretation of the vast amount of data generated by modern analytical methods that is only feasible via elaborate and dedicated (bio)informatic workflows. Thus the Christian Doppler Laboratory had significant support from bioinformatics experts, who finally managed to make sense of the generated data and to materialize the protein heterogeneity hidden in the experimental data. A key experience of mine was the day when Wolfgang Esser-Skala very cautiously explained to me that we cannot just simply subtract the abundance of proteoforms built by chemical attachment of hexoses to lysine residues from the glycosylated proteoforms of the same mass to correct for the corresponding bias in the quantitative glycoform distribution.

Fortunately, Wolfgang readily came up with a graph-based algorithm to correct for the highly complex and interconnected shifts in the abundance of species carrying the isobaric modifications.

A unique experience both for advanced academic researchers as well as bachelor-, master-, and PhD students in the Christian-Doppler Laboratory was to gather insights into the practices of approaching challenges in the pharmaceutical and instrumental industry, including well-defined research problems, distinct milestones, and careful reporting as helpful tools of project management. On the other hand, our partners were also very open to unexpected findings and innovative approaches that could possibly open the doors to novel characterization approaches of protein structures. Nevertheless, it was sometimes challenging to tackle quite diametric interests of commercial production/marketing of pharmaceuticals as well as scientific instruments and the academic goals of performing pure and unbiased scientific research.

Besides more than 40 publications in peer-reviewed scientific journals (for details, see <http://cdl-biosimilars.sbg.ac.at/>), the most valuable output of the Christian-Doppler Laboratory was the teaching and education of 3 Bachelor-, 11 Master-, and 10 PhD students, who either continued their studies or got readily hired to fill interesting and responsible positions mostly in the pharmaceutical and lab instrumentation industry. Moreover, two advanced researchers of the Christian Doppler Laboratory managed to obtain academic lecturing qualification, Gabriele Gadermaier and Therese Wohlschlager. They all represent a well-educated and multidisciplinary network of experts in therapeutic protein characterization ready to spread around the world. In the end we are all very thankful for any kind of support that enabled research in this extremely interesting area of science: from the industry partners Novartis and Thermo Fisher Scientific, from the Christian Doppler Society, from the Allergy Cancer BioNano Research Center, from the Department of Biosciences, from the University of Salzburg, from the State of Salzburg, and too many more to be named individually.

CD Lab members Gabriele Gadermaier (right side) and Therese Wohlschlager (left side) obtaining lecturing qualification in 2019 and 2021.

Christian Huber

What comes next?

Collaborations have been established with the Christian Doppler Laboratory of Mechanistic and Physiological Methods for Improved Bioprocesses installed at the Technical University of Vienna with the ambitious goal of combining molecular characterization attributes as provided by our analytical tools with a comprehensive set of bioprocess parameters together with host-cell “-omics” data in order to derive empirical and mechanistic models for predictable tuning of bioprocesses to obtain desired molecular product quality attributes. A grant proposal for a research group (“DigiTherapeutX: Integrated Digitalized Production of Protein Therapeutics: Linking Molecular Attributes to Process Optimization via Digital Twins”) was submitted to the Austrian Science Fund, and we ask everybody to cross fingers for being successful.

*Christian Huber on behalf of the
Christian Doppler Laboratory for Biosimilar Characterization Team.*

Analysis of Biomedical Visual Data: Model-based vs. Data Driven Research

The group of Andreas Uhl is also known as “Multimedia Signal Processing and Security Lab” (wavelab.at). The group is rooted in the Computer Sciences department and is part of the Visual Computing and Multimedia division. Emphasis of research interests is in the analysis of visual data using model-based and data-driven machine learning techniques, often associated with questions of security and privacy. The group has its focus on application oriented basic research, often driven by methodological research contributions applicable in a real-world context, often in a multi-disciplinary setting. For example, we have published on visual techniques in fish aquaculture, in wood industry (i.e. wood log tracking), automated material hardness measurements, and Blu Ray copy protection systems. Among the application areas considered, the analysis of bio-medical signals has been one of the main topics of interests in the last years: brain-MRI analysis for epilepsy diagnosis, colonoscopy analysis for staging of colon polyps, analysis of duodenal endoscopy data for diagnosis of celiac disease, analysis of various signal types for biometric recognition (e.g. vascular biometrics, iris recognition, fingerprint recognition, EEG-based recognition). Funding is provided by national and European funding bodies.

Due to the recent progress in machine learning and artificial intelligence, we are very interested in the relation between those new approaches and the traditional model-based ones, and to utilise the respective communalities and differences in the development of new, eventually hybrid techniques.

Also, the question for the generation of appropriate domain-specific training data, while respecting the privacy demands and regulations, is of particular interest for our research.

In recent years, the following research topics have been covered:

a) **Computer assisted diagnosis systems:** Based on a cooperation with the St. Anna Children's hospital in Vienna, we have analysed the feasibility of celiac disease diagnosis using duodenal endoscopic video data, both in white light and NBI illumination and several acquisition techniques (e.g., immersion capturing). Furthermore, we have developed techniques for the staging of colonic polyps surface mucosa for various types of illumination. In this context, a wide variability of mucosal feature descriptors have been employed including learning based CNN schemes. Funding was provided by the Austrian Science Fund FWF.

b) **Visual Security Assessment:** The quality and security of cryptographic protection schemes for visual data is known to be difficult to judge. We have investigated the usefulness of known security and quality metrics for this task and found those entirely inappropriate. Thus, we have come up with public datasets of encrypted visual data together with subjective ground truth about their respective security to facilitate the development of better suited visual security metrics. Correlation-based approaches have turned out to be much better suited as compared to schemes employed in literature in particular when it comes to the judgement of intelligibility. We have also investigated in depth the relation between quality and intelligibility and have found significant differences in human observation of these properties. Funding was provided by the Austrian Science Fund FWF where subjective testing has been carried out in a collaboration with the University of Nantes.

c) **Wood-log tracing from forest to sawmill:** The application case for this topic is the question of tracing tree logs from the forest harvesting site to the sawmill by using biometrics related tree log recognition techniques based on image processing of cross-section data only. This approach of course assumes the additional availability of imaging sensors in the forest. Since there is a trend for installing CT imaging devices at sawmills, which are of course not available in the forest, the challenging issue of cross modality matching arises. The techniques developed in this project obviously rely on pattern recognition techniques across different acquisition domains. Funding was provided by the Austrian Science Fund FWF in a French-Austrian international project.

d) **Sensor Forensics:** Digital imaging devices can be uniquely identified based on intrinsic noise-properties of their sensors which originate from the production process. We have particularly looked into specific biometric datasets with their high inter-correlations and have developed techniques for various tasks related to sensor authentication, facial image morphing, deep fake detection, clustering of unknown acquisition devices, and manipulation detection techniques in general. Funding was provided by the Austrian Science Fund FWF, the European Union by their Marie Skłodowska-Curie Research and Innovation Staff Exchange (RISE), and the COST Actions IC1106 and IC1206, respectively.

e) **Vascular Biometrics:** We have developed original sensor hardware as well as new methods for sample processing and recognition for finger vein and hand vein biometric recognition systems. Based on NIR illumination and capturing, these upcoming biometric modalities set new standards in privacy preservation and robustness against acquisition conditions and are expected to compete with more traditional means like fingerprints or palmprint. Funding was provided by the Austrian Science Fund FWF, by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG (in a KIRAS project), and the European Union in a collaborative research and innovation project.

f) **Contact-less Fingerprint Recognition:** The availability of high quality visual sensors in smartphones has initiated a boom to use these devices in various applications of biometric recognition. However, the matching between such samples and samples originating from contact-based scanners (as currently present in most forensic and governmental datasets) is far from being trivial. We develop such techniques by exploiting videos captured with fixed focus from the palmar side of the hand using warping techniques for geometrical correction and stitching techniques to exploit varying quality across frames. Funding was provided by the Austrian Research Promotion Agency FFG (in a KIRAS project).

g) **Tools for Generation of Synthetic Sample Data:** Acquisition of training data for machine learning applications (e.g., in medical imaging) or biometric sample data to run large scale experiments is difficult and often hindered by privacy protection legislation (e.g., GDPR). We have worked on methodology to generate and evaluate synthetic data for such tasks that are close to natural data in many ways, ranging from visual inspection to stringent statistical analysis. Funding was provided by the Austrian Science Fund FWF in an international DFG-FWF project.

Currently, the group is starting a new project funded by the government of the state of Salzburg and five companies focusing on machine learning issues related to visual data analysis, in particular related to the lack of sufficiently annotated training data and ways how to cope with this often seen limitation in industrial vision problems. As it is the case in this new project, also topics a) – g) mostly involve the processing and analysis of biological or biomedical signals, so that we expect a fruitful collaboration with the groups of the ACBN Research Centre.

Andreas Uhl

Andreas Uhl

ACBN @ many (beautiful) places

ACBN @
Science City
Salzburg Itzling

ACBN @
"NaWi"
Hellbrunnerstraße

*Thanks to
Theresa Neuper, Andreas Uhl and
Luigi Caputo for all these pictures!*

400 years Paris Lodron University Salzburg

In the upcoming year 2022, the Paris Lodron University of Salzburg (PLUS) will celebrate the 400th anniversary of its founding and at the same time the 60th anniversary since it was re-established in 1962. To mark the anniversary year in due style, an extensive program of events was created.

Today we would like to draw your attention to some of the **event highlights** and kindly ask you to make a note of the dates:

Wed, January 26, 2022, 6 p.m., state rooms of the Salzburg Residence, Carabinierisaal

Opening of the anniversary exhibition in the DomQuartier Salzburg and presentation of the accompanying book "PLUSpunkte. 400 years of the University of Salzburg"

Fri, February 4, 2022, 7 p.m., Salzburg Residence

PLUS Gala: A festive evening

With Klaus Maria Brandauer | Sabine Meyer, clarinet, Lübeck University of Music | Michèle Crider, soprano, Mozarteum University

Thu, May 5, 2022, 7 p.m., Large University Auditorium (Große Aula)

Salzburg lecture: "The future of science: Between autonomy and social mandate."

With Anton Zeilinger, President of the Austrian Academy of Sciences | Renée Schröder, Biochemist | Elisabeth Gutjahr, Rector of the Mozarteum University Salzburg | Hendrik Lehnert, Rector of the Paris Lodron University of Salzburg

Fri, June 24, 2022, 7 p.m., Unipark Nonntal

Alumni Festival for the 20th anniversary of the Alumni Club

For our anniversary, we invite all friends of the university to send us a little greeting.

Tue, October 4, 2022, 5 p.m., Large University Auditorium (Große Aula)
Academic reception of the rector on the day the university was founded

Lecture series in the summer semester 2022:

400PLUS lectures

Nine exciting lectures, including Jutta Allmendinger, President of the Berlin Science Center for Social Research

“400 Voices for 400 Years of the PLUS”

Perhaps you would like to send us your congratulations as well, memories or a small comment on PLUS in a few lines. These will be published on the PLUS homepage with your name and ideally also with a photo of yourself.

Please send us your message and photo to 400stimmen@plus.ac.at
Maximum text length: 300 characters (incl. spaces). If you send in a photo, please also provide the photo credit (e.g.: Photo: © name of photographer).

*We wish you all a Happy and Peaceful Holiday time
and a Successful and Healthy New Year 2022!*

Image references:

Paris-Lodron-University of Salzburg, Luigi Caputo, Andreas Uhl, Theresa Neuper, Christian Doppler
Laboratory for Biosimilar Characterization / C. Huber

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